

A Study on the Post Marriage Problems in India

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Abstract :

The family is not a static institution. In recent decades, marriage rates have fallen, divorce rates have risen, and the defining characteristics of marriage have changed. The economic approach to the family seeks to explain these trends by reference to models that can also explain how and why families form. Increased longevity and declining fertility mean that most of one's adult life is spent without one's own children in the household, and the rise in marital formation at older ages, including re-marriage, means that many families form with no intention of producing children.

Introduction :

Marriages can be challenging for most people as it involves melding your life and goals with someone else's. Marriage problems after kids or other major changes can be challenging to deal with and can lead to resentment and feelings of disappointment. Marriage problems, however, are often a result of complacent behavior and oversight. These problems can be resolved with the right approach and openness to reflect.

The family is not a static institution. In recent decades, marriage rates have fallen, divorce rates have risen, and the defining characteristics of marriage have changed. The economic approach to the family seeks to explain these trends by

reference to models that can also explain how and why families form. Treatise on the Family proposed a theory based on “production complementarities”, in which husband and wife specialize in the market and domestic spheres, respectively, and hence are more productive together than apart. Production complementarities also arise in the production and rearing of one’s own children. However, production complementarities at least as initially described are decreasingly central to modern family life.

Common post Marriage problems :

➤ Communication Issues :

The most common complaint among married couples is lack of communication. Many couples put up with problems rather than try to fix them. In the beginning they agreed he would earn money and she would take care of the house and kids. When they face new challenges later on, they have to negotiate a new compact.

➤ Ignoring Boundaries :

It’s not uncommon for one spouse to try to change his or her partner. Whether it’s how he or she dresses or about fundamental beliefs, trying to change their spouse will feel like a personal invasion and may trigger defensiveness or anger. Overstepping boundaries can destroy mutual trust.

➤ Lack of appreciation :

A lack of gratitude, recognition, and acknowledgment of spouse’s towards contribution on their relationship. The inability to appreciate the spouse can be detrimental to your relationship.

➤ Non-Sex relationship :

There are lots of reasons couples lose interest in sex-ranging from medical problems to emotional issues. Generally, sexual problems trigger a vicious cycle where it’s difficult to want sex when they feel emotionally distant from their partner and it’s difficult to feel emotionally attached without experiencing sexual intimacy.

➤ **Selfishness :**

If one spouse constantly places his or her needs above the goals and interests of the marriage, it's only a matter of time before the neglected spouse begins to feel rejected and unloved.

➤ **Value Differences :**

Couples may have major disagreements about what religion to teach their children. Other differences include how to discipline, definitions of right and wrong, or other ethical conflicts. Everyone doesn't grow up with the same values, morals, or goals and there is lots of room for debate about right and wrong.

➤ **Financial Issues :**

Nothing can break a marriage faster than money. If you are opening a joint account or handling your finances separately, you will encounter financial problems in your marriage. It is essential to discuss any financial issues as a couple openly.

➤ **Different Life Stages :**

Personalities change and a couple may not remain compatible as they transition to different life stages. An older husband may not be interested in beginning a new family while the young bride is anxious to have a baby, or he may be nearing retirement and want to slow down while she needs to stay active.

➤ **Boredom :**

Doing the same old thing can get tiresome and it's hard to make changes in a comfortable relationship until it's too late. Doing something new from time to time can add spark and spice to a relationship.

➤ **Jealousy :**

Being jealous can turn a marriage sour, especially if the jealous feelings are unrealistic. Jealous persons can become overbearing and controlling or angry and rejecting. If they are feeling jealous, see a counselor to decide whether the feelings are reasonable. They may have an attachment problem that needs to be discussed with a competent counselor.

Conclusion :

However, in order to live a happy married life, it is essential to accept your spouse the way they are. Everyone has different beliefs, thinking patterns, opinions, and viewpoints. So it is natural that no two people think alike. Hence, it can be said that marriage is a merger of two separate sets of beliefs and mindsets. Due to these unlike mindsets, a couple tends to differ in terms of the way they deal with different matters in life. These differences create conflict in marriage, thus resulting in an unhappy marriage.

References :

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